

Humanistic management and the counterproductive behaviours as perceived by the employees

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to determine the effect of the humanistic management style of administrators on the counterproductive work behaviour of employees. To deepen the understanding of the concepts and to establish the theories of the study, literature was reviewed. The study used descriptive assessment and a correlational research design. The population of the study was all employees and administrators of Divine Word College of Laoag. Questionnaires were used to gather the data and weighted mean and Pearson *r* correlation was used to analyze the data. The study found that the humanistic management style of administrators is high and counterproductive behaviour is low. However, Pearson *r* correlation indicated that there is no significant correlation between humanistic management style and counterproductive behaviour of employees. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected.

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Introduction

Managing employees' work performance is a complex one because it is not just a matter of improving employees' skills and related knowledge to the work, they perform but it also involves managing their behaviour. Skills and knowledge are not the only factors that improve their performance but their behaviour may affect the output of their work. Ignoring their work behaviour may suffer individual and organizational performance. However, managing employees' behaviour starts with how management manages and leads his/her people. Treating employees humanly may affect their attitude and behaviour and thus affects work engagement (Abun, et.al, 2021). Simbine and Tukamushaba and Simbine (2020) had pointed out the effect of the behaviour of employees on organizational competitiveness. The study found that employees' behaviour directly affects organizational competitiveness and pointed out further that the behaviours are affected by the extent of employees' involvement in decision-making and the level of employees' salary.

Many issues on turnover and retention are related to how the management treats the employees in the workplace. For example, in the case of turnover issue, Olobiyi, et.al (2019) pointed out the reasons for employee turnover in the retail business namely friendly workplace environment, flexibility, stability, management support, and independence. This study indirectly suggests that an unfriendly workplace environment, inflexibility, instability, no support, and no autonomy are the drivers of employee turnover. Concerning issues on retention, Scott (2008) singled out several reasons why the employees stay with the company such as employees' work-life balance, job sharing, job redesign, compressed work schedules, appropriate accommodations of religious beliefs and

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practices, illnesses, and grief over the loss of loved ones. In other words, management must not sacrifice employees' personal lives because of work and consider or accommodate employees' personal beliefs and other situations in the decision-making process. These reasons could be classified into organizational, personal, and psycho-social factors of employee turnover as pointed out by Reyes, et.al (2019). Thus, it is a challenge on the management's side to create joy in the workplace (Jalilianhansapour, et.al, 2021). How to create joy in the workplace? Jalilianhansapour, et.al, (2021) recommended the tips such as a management approach on how to augment feelings of worth, appreciation, and well-being of employees. Thus, management must pay attention to a physical and psychosocial workplace that promotes the happiness of employees through little things like appreciation, mindfulness, humour, playfulness, and fitful lifestyle choices (Jalilianhansapour, et.al, (2021). Giving attention to these humanistic issues inspires the productive behaviour of employees.

The reasons for turnover as pointed out by the research mentioned above are not exclusively found in manufacturing industries, and retail businesses but even in educational institutions. In other words, humanistic issues are all over different industries, and therefore it is one of management's concerns. Many faculties and employees in the educational institution leave their work because of many reasons and one of the reasons is humanistic treatment. Humanistic treatment suggests that management must look at the workforce as humans first and not machines that can be manipulated. Employees are human beings with dignity and since they have dignity, the management must respect the employees. A form of respect can be translated into the human treatment of employees.

This is the concern of the paper. It investigates the effect of humanistic management on the counterproductive behaviour of employees. Based on the literature review, this is the first study to be conducted related to humanistic management and its effect on the behaviour of employees. Thus, this study fills the vacuum of research along with this concern. It will be divided into several parts. The first part is the introduction which explains the background and rationale of the study. The second part is the literature review that examines past literature related to the current topic which helps establish the theories of the current study. The third part is the research methodology which discusses the research design, population or sampling, locale, research instruments, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Literature Review

To understand the concept of humanistic management, it is important to review the existing literature and previous studies that discusses the theories of humanistic management and its effect on the organization and employees' behaviour. The purpose is to establish the fundamental theories on the issue and consequently help the researcher to understand deeper the topic of investigation. Following such purpose, the presentation of the literature review will be arranged thematically and it will be divided into two parts namely theoretical concepts and studies and the conceptual framework of the study.

Theoretical and Conceptual Background

The Concept of Human Dignity and its Violation

The word dignity comes from the Latin word "dignus and Dignitas" which means worthiness for honour and esteem (Schulman, 2008). In the German language, it is called "Würde" and translated as "dignity" or "worth". This classical concept of dignity continues to gain its power in all human affairs as it develops into a different aspect of human life. The concept of dignity was further developed by Kant and has influenced a wide range of moral and political philosophers. The concept of human dignity has gained the attention of many people, philosophers, and organizations that guide human affairs in society. It is always used as a mirror to see if all actions and laws are not violating human dignity. It is always the basis for the state, and organizations to formulate laws. For example, United Nations formulated the International Covenant on Human Rights (1966) based on the concept of human dignity which becomes the moral basis for human rights. Kretzmer and Klein (2002) pointed out that the recognition of the dignity and inalienable rights of all members of the human family is the foundation of freedom, justice, and peace in society. Human dignity is the inherent value that all human beings possess (Sensen, 2011). It is the heart of human rights. Immanuel Kant defined dignity as absolute inner value (Sensen, 2011) and it becomes the unconditional basis for respecting one another (Sensen, 2011). This concept leads us to the way how we treat one another. In the case of how we treat one another or how we should act toward other human beings, Immanuel Kant Proposed the humanity formula which states, "So act that you use humanity, whether in your person or the person of any other, always at the same time as an end, never merely as a means" (Sensen, 2011). The dignity of a human person lies in his/her unique position as a rational being. Human beings are raised above other creatures because of the possession of reason (Sensen, 2011) which Shell (2008) called embodied rationality. Dignity designates value that has no equivalent which is beyond price (Shell, 2008). This is concerning what Kant as cited by Rachels (1986) had pointed out that human beings have an "intrinsic worth" which is called dignity and it makes them valuable "above all price". Human dignity is a recognition that human beings possess an intrinsic value and thus are worthy of respect because they are simply human beings (Dennett, 2008) with reasons which make them higher than other creators. Above the reason (rationality), in the Christian view, there is a divine ground for human dignity because humans are created in the image of God which is called Imago Dei" (Haack, 2012). The Imago Dei concept emphasizes the central concern for equality among human beings which disallows humans to degrade another human being. Thus, the recognition of human dignity is an acceptance that all human beings hold a special value that is inherent to their humanity by possessing reason or rationality and the image of God. Along with this concept, Pope Leo XIII (1891) in the late 19th century condemned the situation in factories where employers laid the burdens on employees to the extent of degrading their human dignity as human beings. The Pope then exhorted

employers to respect workers as human beings with dignity (Pope Leo XIII, 1891). With the same concern, the United Nations and other international organizations have called for businesses to be more human and ethical (Mele, 2016). Along with the call for ethical and human treatment of employees, thus business ethics was introduced (Kleinfeld et al, 2003). For the question of how we respect human beings, we simply go back to what Immanuel Kant suggested to treat human beings as the end and not means. As compared to animals, humans are ends in themselves but animals are means to an end which suggests that humans have no direct responsibility to refrain from harming animals because they are not important as compared to human beings (Rachels, 1986). Humans can use animals in the way they please but humans cannot be used as means to an end (Rachels, 1986) and this is the ultimate law of morality from which our duties and obligations are derived.

Inhuman treatment is considered a violation of human dignity (Kaufmann, et.al, 2011). Kaufmann, et.al (2011) identified several practices that are considered a violation of human dignity namely humiliation, instrumentalization, degradation, and dehumanization. Humiliation refers to any behaviour or conditions that constitute a reason for a person to consider her/his self-respect injured ((Margalit 1996). According to Margalit (1996), humiliation may happen through actual behaviour directed toward a person which can be behaviours that may be considered humiliating others and it can be also through conditions that degrade self-respect. In other words, someone can feel humiliated without being humiliated. Humiliation is an attempt to degrade someone below the status of a human being as a person of dignity. Therefore, degrading treatment is considered a humiliation. While instrumentalization refers to the use of a human person for a certain end. Using people for a certain end is treating people as tools or objects to be used for a certain purpose. Using people is considered a violation of human dignity when it is done without the consent of the other party to perform a certain act (Kaufmann, et.al, 2011). It is also the same case with degradation. Degradation refers to degrading treatment such as the condition of confinement, corporal punishment, strip searches, and failure to provide adequate food and health care. It is often referring to treatment that lowers someone to a less respected state (Webster, 2011). Degrading treatment is considered a violation of human dignity. Dehumanization is another case of violation of human dignity. Dehumanization refers to inhuman treatment which prevents individuals to experience and live positive human qualities of individuality, autonomy, personality, civility, and living dignity (Oliver, 2011). Kaufmann, et.al. (2011) identified some other practices that are seen as a violation of human dignity such as torture, rape, social exclusion, absolute poverty, labour exploitation, and bonded labour.

Violation of human dignity through inhuman treatment does happen everywhere including in how the organization manages its employees. Where does it go wrong? Steyaert and Jnassens (1999) pointed out that it all starts from the concept of human resources. Human resources management was originally introduced to maximize human potential through selecting, appraising, rewarding, and developing employees to achieve better outcomes such as competence, commitment, quality, and cost-effectiveness. It was a way of improving productivity and quality. However, despite its benefits for the organization, it is also a reality that organizations have been treating human beings or employees as a cost and resource (Steyaert and Jnassens,1999). When the organization sees its employees as cost, then it would be cut anytime when it is not contributing value to the organization. The concern of maximizing profits leads to minimized costs which lead to downsizing or rightsizing. This has been the management strategy in a time of crisis. Thus, such a view lead to considering the employees as liabilities which in time of economic crisis, employees can be laid off (Cascio, 2003). Consequently, seeing employees as resources has affected the way how management treats employees. It somehow sees employees as objects or commodities to be used, not as creative and social beings in a productive enterprise and therefore the management tries different strategies to make these objects useful and resourceful.

Inhuman treatment takes its form in the bureaucratic management style. Bureaucracy has been touted to be promoting efficiency, productivity and rationality through following rules, and procedures in performing one's duties and responsibilities (Abun, et.al, 2021). However, such a management style has been criticized by many experts. For example, Kang (2005) criticized it as a burden for people to follow rules without flexibility. Rose-Ackerman, (1986), Peters, (1993), and Preston, (1987) considered recognized it as a form of ineffective management. Merton (1952) accused it as a cause of inefficiency and irrationality. Bodley (2002) saw it as inhuman because it forces people to follow rules, procedures, and the command of authority blindly and workers cannot exercise their sense of right and wrong in performing their tasks.

The Concept of Humanistic Management and Practices

To understand the humanistic management style, one needs to understand the terms in the first place. Defining the humanistic term cannot be done without understanding the meaning of humanism because both terms are interrelated. According to the Merriam-Webster dictionary, humanism means " devotion to humanities" or "devotion to human welfare" or " a doctrine, attitude, or way of life centred on human interest or values, especially a philosophy that usually rejects supernaturalism and stresses an individual's dignity and worth and capacity for self-realization through reason". American Humanist Association (n.d) defines humanism as "a rational philosophy informed by science, inspired by art, and motivated by compassion". This definition confirms the dignity of human beings and recognizes individual liberty and participatory democracy and protection of human rights and social justice. The definition of humanism becomes important when we define the humanistic term. Humanistic is defined by Collins Dictionary as "condition or practice relates to humanism". While Merriam Webster defines it as " relating to humanism" or " treating people with respect and making certain they are safe, happy, healthy". Thus, based on the definitions offered by these dictionaries, we define humanistic as "practices that are based on humanism principles".

The concept of humanistic management is not far from the definitions that are found in these dictionaries and as provided by the American Humanist Association. Humanistic management refers to management practices that focus on human concern. In other words, it orients toward serving human ends and not profit (Mele, 2016). It is an alternative to mechanistic management (Mele, 2016) or bureaucratic management which is often accused by many of inhuman, dehumanizing humans to the level of objects to be manipulated (Bodley, 2002, Merton, 1952, Pretson, 1987). Humanistic management is an effort to balance the attention on how the organization should be managed. The focus should not be solely on the mechanistic side of management which focuses on a rule, procedures, and the hierarchy of command which dictates the employees simply to follow the procedures, rules, and the authority blindly but management must consider the human side which dictates the management treat employees as human beings with dignity. The message is so simple that the technical aspect of the job is not separated from the human aspect as Follet (141) argued that one cannot separate the human from mechanical problems. The concern for human welfare in management is nothing new because it was also the concern of earlier management theorists such as Maslow, McGregor, Herzberg, and others, though they were not termed it as humanistic management but simply a management strategy to motivate employees to work (Mele, 2016). The term was coined by Lilienthal (1967) in his book: "Management: A Humanistic Art". These theorists realized that giving attention to human needs are strategies that should be prioritized to motivate employees to perform better in their job. Thus, the priority should not be on the rules, procedures, and obedience to the authority but on human needs which include physical and psychological needs. As Peter Drucker pointed out that management is about humans or about people which stressing on the importance of the wholeness of the person along with power, values, structure, and responsibilities (Linkletter and Maciariello 2011; Maciariello 2014). The emphasis on the wholeness of the human person is a moral command to respect human dignity which is central to humanistic management (von Kimakowitz, 2011).

Based on the concept of humanistic management that we have discussed above, thus the central concern of humanistic management includes the unconditional respect for human dignity, integration of ethical concern in management decisions, and the active and ongoing engagement with the stakeholders (von Kimakowitz, 2011). The concern of the management is how to treat employees in the workplace with respect. Heathfield (2021), a human resources expert suggested some ways that we can apply the management practices such as acknowledging each person's dignity, empathizing with the person's life situation, listening to and encouraging employees' opinions and inputs, and recognizing employees' contributions and avoiding unprofessional behaviours. Abun, et.al (2021) identified several practices to be considered humanistic practices such as allowing employees to exercise the freedom to carry out their tasks, considering ideas of employees when making decisions, prioritizing the needs of employees, listening to employees when they have problems, respecting and treating employees as human beings with dignity, recognizing the contribution of employees, opening communication line between employees and management, and considering the effect of the decisions to the life of employees. In this case, the proper management styles to be practised are participative or democratic management and a liberal style of management. Practising a democratic management style implies that the management recognizes employees to be the rational being who possess ideas and therefore allows employees to share views, and recommends solutions (Hornáčková, et.al. 2015). The same case with a liberal management style. This style recognizes employees to be rational beings and possess free will. Consequently, the management should allow a certain extent of autonomy and freedom or independence in which the employees are allowed to set their goals and the means to achieve those goals (Hornáčková, et.al. 2015). Beyond treating employees with respect, humanistic management requires ethical concern in decision making as recommended by von Kimakowitz (2011). In the absence of common ground for the universal ethical decision process, it may help to look into what Kitchener (1984), and Kitchener and Kitchener, (2012) recommended as guidance in ethical decision-making considerations namely nonmaleficence or do no harm to others, beneficence or produce good, respect for autonomy or respect the right of others to make their decision as long as their decisions do not harm others, justice or fair, fidelity or are truthful and keeping the promises (Kitchener, 2016).

Counterproductive Behavior

Work behaviour matters in any organization. This is one of management's concerns that need to be given serious attention. Monitoring individual work behaviour is important to detect as early as possible behaviours that may harm the organization. However, monitoring employees' work behaviour and preventing counterproductive behaviour needs an analysis of the causes of different behaviours. Through psychology, one understands that motivation causes behaviour. It is the motivation that initiates, guides, and maintains a goal-oriented behaviour (Cherry, 2020). The level of motivation causes a certain extent of behaviour and it causes different behaviour from one employee to another employee. The force behind these behaviours can be biological, emotional, or cognitive (Cherry, 2021). This theory suggests that managers need to review factors that contribute to biological, emotional, and cognitive motivation and address the discrepancies. It is also through psychology one knows that behaviour is also caused by attitude as presented by Ajzen (1993) and as cited by Abun, et.al (2021). One's attitude toward work affects the behaviour and work performance (Abun, et.al 2021), Abdalkrim and Elhalim (2016). This theory also recommends that managers need to assess and know the attitude of employees toward their work. In this case, the manager needs to know employees' cognitive attitudes and affective attitudes toward their work. A low level of cognitive and affective attitude toward work may affect their work behaviour and work performance. Social psychologist, Albert Bandura (1977) also pointed out that environmental and cognitive factors influence behaviour. Bandura (1977) argued that environmental and cognitive elements affect behaviour. He pointed out that behaviour is learned from the environment through observation. This theory suggests that understanding the behaviour of employees needs a review of the organizational environment that may affect the behaviour of employees. Studies on organizational behaviour found that certain levels of job or work

satisfaction cause different employees' work behaviour, performance, and commitment such as one finds in the study of Wright (2006), Culibrk, et.al (2018), Borst, et.al (2019), and Tafzal Haque, et.al (2019). These studies also remind the managers that behaviour is a complex phenomenon that needs to be analyzed well to determine exactly the causes of counterproductive behaviour. Monitoring the level of job satisfaction is one important concern of the management.

Organizational success starts from individual employees' work behaviour or work performance. Thus, it requires behavioural management which demands a thorough analysis of different aspects that affect the employees' behaviour. In this regard, motivation, attitude, and organizational environment need to be assessed to determine the causes of different behaviours of employees. The purpose is to detect as early as possible counterproductive behaviours that may suffer negative outcomes for the organization. Counterproductive behaviours have been defined as "employee voluntary behaviours that harm organizations (CWB-O) or people working in the organizations (CWB-P)" (Zhou, 2020). Examples of counterproductive work behaviour include destroying a company's property, calling in sick when he/she is not, insulting another employee, and stealing something from the employer (Zhou, 2020). These behaviours harm the company's performance. APA Dictionary of Psychology (n.d) defines counterproductive work behaviour as "undesirable employee behaviour that can undermine the goals of an organization or its members and can negatively affect the organization's financial well-being". It identifies several behaviours that are considered counterproductive such as sabotage, theft, absenteeism, bullying, sexual harassment, discrimination, workplace violence, drug and alcohol abuse, and violation of confidentiality agreements (APA Dictionary of Psychology, n.d).

Studies have been done by several researchers concerning the effect of counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) on work performance and engagement such as Bagyo (2018), on the organization, stakeholders of the organization, public image, and its professional counterparts (Karthikeyan & Thomas, 2017), on organizational citizenship behaviours (Sypniewska, 2020), and organizational climate, occupational status, and leader-member exchange (Chernyak-Hai & Tziner, 2014). These studies have found that counterproductive work behaviour (CWB) affects individual and organizational performance negatively. These studies recommend that serious attention must be given to monitoring counterproductive behaviours of employees because it does not only affect the performance of the organization and the performance of employees but also affects the organizational public image.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual framework reflects the objective of the study. It aims to examine the effect of the humanistic management style on the counterproductive behaviour of employees; *Source:* Abun, et.al (2021) and Koopmans, et.al (2014).

Statement of the Problems

The study aims to examine the effect of humanistic management on the counterproductive behaviour of employees. It specifically seeks to answer the following questions:

- i. What is the humanistic management style of administrators?
- ii. What is the counterproductive behaviour of employees?
- iii. Is there a relationship between humanistic management style and counterproductive behaviour?

Assumption

The study assumes that humanistic management affects the work performance of employees specifically along with counterproductive behaviour and it can be measured.

Hypothesis

Bousari, et.al (2020) studied the impact of ethical leadership styles on counterproductive behaviour and found that leadership style impacts counterproductive behaviour in the workplace. Thus, the current study hypothesizes that humanistic management styles affect the counterproductive behaviour of employees in the workplace.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study limits its investigation to the administrators and employees of school X and delimits its investigation only to humanistic management practices and counterproductive behaviour.

Research and Methodology

Scientific research must follow a research methodology. It follows a specific procedure or technique to identify, select, process, and analyze information about a topic (Wilkinson, 2000, Leedy, 1974). An academic research paper must follow the method of investigation. Along with such requirements, the current study follows the rule of procedures in the investigation by following a certain research design, data gathering instruments method, the population of the study, the locale of the study, the data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design of the study

The study used a descriptive assessment and correlational research design to determine the level of the humanistic management styles of administrators as perceived by the employees and its effect on counterproductive behaviour. Ariola (2006) contended that a descriptive correlation study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, or phenomena. In short, it answers the question of what, when, how, where, and not why question (McCombes, 2020).

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines.

Population

The respondents of the study are the employees of the college. Since the number of employees is limited, therefore, the total enumeration sampling was used and thus all (160) faculty and employees were taken as respondents to the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The study adapted validated questionnaires of Abun, et.al. (2021) on Humanistic management style and Koopmans, et.al (2014) on counterproductive behaviour.

Data Gathering Procedures

To maintain the integrity of the investigation and to ensure that the data are gathered through the right process, thus, before the researcher distributes the questionnaires, a letter was sent to the President of the college to request them to allow the researcher to float his questionnaires in the institution. In the process of collecting the data, the researcher requests employee representatives to retrieve the data from different individual employees before they are submitted to the researcher.

Ethical Procedures

The study was carried out after the research ethics committee examined and approved the content of the paper if it does not violate ethical standards and if it does not cause harm to human life and the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, descriptive and inferential statistic was used. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of the humanistic management style of administrators and counterproductive behaviour, and the Pearson r was used to measure the correlation between humanistic management style and counterproductive behaviour of employees.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

Data Presentation and Analysis

This part presents the data that was gathered through research questionnaires and analyzed through SPSS statistical analysis tool. The data presentation analysis follows the arrangement of the statement of the problems.

Problem 1: What is the humanistic management style of administrators?

Table 1: Humanistic Management Style of the Administrators

Indicators	Mean	DR
1. Employees are allowed to exercise their freedom to carry out their tasks.	3.86	A
2. Employees are rewarded for giving new ideas on how to solve their problems	3.64	A
3. The management considers the ideas of employees when making decisions	3.73	A
4. The management always tries their best to serve the needs of employees	3.64	A
5. The management listens to the employees when the employees counter problems in their work.	3.59	A
6. The management respect and treat the employees as human beings with dignity.	3.69	A
7. The management recognizes the good effort of the employees to help the institution	3.66	A
8. There is open communication between employees and management	3.64	A
9. When making decisions, the management always considers the effect of the decision on the employees	3.56	A
10. The management put the employees first before the work.	3.49	A
Composite Mean	3.65	A

Source: Abun, et al (2021)

Based on the data presented in the table, shows that as a whole, the humanistic management of administrators at Divine Word College of Laoag obtained a composite mean of 3.65 which is considered "agree/high". This composite mean suggests that the humanistic management of the administrators is not very high and it is also not very low, low or moderate but it is high. Even if the indicators are taken singly, all indicators are rated within the same level mean range with the same interpretation as " agree/high" such as allowing employees to exercise the freedom to carry out their tasks, respecting and treating employees as human beings with dignity, rewarding employees who can provide ideas to solve problems, accommodating the ideas of employees when making decisions, serving the needs of the employees, listening to employees when employees encounter a problem at work, recognizing the effort of the employees, open communication between employees and management, considering the effect of their decisions on the employees and putting employees first before work.

These results indicate that the administrators of the Divine Word College of Laoag practice humanistic management to a high degree, though it is not to a very high degree. There is still room for improvement. Humanistic management is people-oriented management that seeks profit for human ends (Mele, 2016). It is not human for-profit ends which is in contrast to other kinds of management which is profit-oriented, not human-oriented.

Problem 2: What is the counterproductive behaviour of employees?

Table 2: The Counterproductive Behavior of Employees

Indicators	Mean	DR
1. I complained about unimportant matters at work.	2.23	D
2. I made problems greater than they were at work.	2.10	D
3. I focused on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of on the positive aspects.	2.06	D
4. I spoke with colleagues about the negative aspects of my work.	2.33	D
5. I spoke with people from outside the organization about the negative aspects of my work	2.23	D
6. I did less than was expected of me.	2.16	D
7. I managed to get off from a work task easily.	2.30	D
8. I sometimes did nothing, while I should have been working 1 2 3 4 5	2.09	D
Composite Mean	2.19	D

Source: Koopmans, et al (2014).

The data on the table shows that as a whole counterproductive behaviour of the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag gained a composite mean of 2.19 which is interpreted as “disagree/low”. This composite mean indicates that as a whole the counterproductive behaviours of employees are not very high or high and it is also not very low or moderate but it is low. Even if the indicators are taken singly, all indicators are assessed within the same level mean range with the same descriptive interpretation as “disagree/low” such as complaining about unimportant matters at work, making problems greater than they were at work, focusing on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of the positive aspects, speaking with colleagues about the negative aspects of the work, speaking with people outside the institution about the negative aspects of the work, doing less than what is expected of them, managing to get out of work easily and did nothing while they should have been working.

These results recommend that the counterproductive behaviour of the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag is low, though it is not very low. This suggests that there is room for improvement. Counterproductive behaviour refers to voluntary behaviours that harm the organization as a whole and harm coworker (Zhou, 2020). Examples of those behaviours are complaining about unimportant

matters, always pointing out the negative aspect of the work and the institution to the outsiders or insiders, exaggerating little problems, destroying company properties, etc. Counterproductive behaviours are the opposite of contextual work performance or organizational behaviour (Sypniewska, 2020).

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between humanistic management style and counterproductive behaviour?

Table 3: Relationship between Humanistic Management Style and Counterproductive Behavior

		Counterproductive Behavior
Humanistic Management Style	Pearson Correlation	0.083
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.298
	N	160

Source: SPSS

No Relationship

Based on the Pearson Correlation table, reveals that there is a significant relationship between humanistic management style and counterproductive work behaviour. It means that in the context of Divine Word College of Laoag, the humanistic management style has nothing to do with counterproductive behaviour. In other words, a lower level of counterproductive behaviour is not necessarily caused by a high humanistic management style alone but there can be other factors that are not included in the study as the cause of counterproductive behaviour like justice perception such as distributive, procedural, interpersonal and informational justice (Cochran, 2014). It can also be caused by the culture and personality of leaders (Shen & Lei, 2022).

Result and Discussion

The study aimed to examine the effect of the humanistic management style of administrators on the counterproductive behaviour of employees. Statistical analysis shows that the humanistic management style is considered high and counterproductive work behaviour of employees is low. However, lower counterproductive behaviour of employees is not necessarily caused by the humanistic management style of the administrators because the result of the Pearson r correlation indicates that there is no significant correlation between the humanistic management style of administrators and lower counterproductive behaviour of employees. Lower counterproductive work behaviour employees can be caused by other factors that were not considered by the current study. Besides the factors that were considered earlier, it is also important to see culture as one of the factors that may control or motivate deviant behaviour as pointed out by Taylor (2012). Cultural dimensions such as assertiveness, human orientation, in-group collectivism, institutional collectivism, and uncertainty avoidance (Taylor, 2012) can explain why employees of Divine Word College of Laoag have low counterproductive behaviour.

The result of the study contributes to the enrichment of the discussion of counterproductive behaviour topics. Investigating counterproductive behaviour should not be limited to single variables which is the limitation of the current study but it should include many other factors like society’s culture and organizational culture. Society’s culture can motivate or control deviant behaviour as pointed out by Taylor (2012). Therefore, the current study recommends next study include more variables such as society and organizational culture in the study of counterproductive behaviour.

Conclusion

The study aims to determine the effect of the humanistic management style of administrators on the counterproductive workplace behaviour of the employees of Divine Word College of Laoag. The result indicates that the humanistic management style is high and counterproductive behaviour is low. Such result suggests that the higher the humanistic management styles, the lower the counterproductive behavior becomes. The Pearson r correlation indicates that there is no correlation between the humanistic management style of administrators and the counterproductive work behaviour of employees. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study is rejected. In other words, in the context of Divine Word College of Laoag, counterproductive work behaviour is not associated or correlated with a humanistic management style but other organizational factors that are not taken by this study. Concerning this result, it is recommended that future study should be conducted to include more organizational factors to determine which of them that cause counterproductive work behaviour.

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